

Research Article

Combining Ability Analysis in F₁ Hybrids of Cotton (*Gossypium Species* L.) by Diallel Method in Northeastern Nigeria

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ARTICLE INFO

Article No.: 101812119

DOI: 10.15580/GJAS.2013.2.101812119

Submitted: 18/10/2012

Accepted: 30/10/2012

Published: 20/02/2013

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Keywords:

Combining ability, hybrids, generations, cotton, diallel, F₁

ABSTRACT

Crosses were made between eight cotton genotypes in a full diallel crossing pattern in 2005/2006 at the Research Farm of the School of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Yola. The resulting 56 F₁ hybrids along with their parents were evaluated in the cropping season of 2007 in Yola, Adamawa State and Sibre, Taraba State. Also, the resulting F₂ hybrids and their parental lines were evaluated in 2008 at Yola and Sibre, Adamawa and Taraba States in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications in each location. The study investigated the type of gene effects and mode of inheritance of quantitative characters among F₁ population of cotton, the GCA effects of the parent, SCA effects of the hybrids, reciprocal effects and maternal effects. The analysis of variance indicated that there were significant differences among the cotton populations for most of the characters evaluated in terms of level of significant influence of the environments on the different sources of variation and their interactions with each other and the environments. The study revealed that general combining ability (GCA) effect was lower than specific combining ability (SCA) effect for most of the characters evaluated; suggesting that inheritance of these characters is governed mainly by non additive gene effects. The study identified SAMCOT 11, EX-Benin, SAMCOT 8 and SAMCOT 13 to be the best general combiners for most of the important yield components in both populations. SAMCOT 10 x SAMCOT 11 and SAMCOT 10 x SAMCOT 11 were identified as the best specific combiners among the F₁ hybrids for early maturity and yield.

INTRODUCTION

Cotton, (*Gossypium species L*) is an important crop world over and its utilization and cultivation is on the increase. Cotton is not grown for subsistence. It is an important source of cash income for farmers. It is one of the two most important cash crops in the northern states of Nigeria beside groundnut. (Idem, 1999). Important Countries for cotton production in tropical Africa are Sudan, Coted'Ivoire, Nigeria, Chad, Mali, Tanzania, and Angola (Onwuema and Sinha, 1991).

The total production of seed cotton in Nigeria between 2001 and 2003 ranged from 381,000 metric tones to 403,000 metric tones (FAO, 2004). Between the early 1980s and the peak of 2005, cotton production has progressed twice as quickly in sub-sahara Africa as elsewhere in the world. (Spores, 2009). The net area under cotton production in Nigeria during the 2001 season was 542,000 hectare which increased to 611,000 hectare in 2002, but later dropped slightly to 610,000 hectare in 2003 (FAO, 2004). Nigeria's cotton lint production was reported by Ali (2004) to increase to 100,000 metric tones in 2004 from 85,000 metric tones in 2003 due to attractive producer price and favourable rainfall pattern during the 2004 season. The yields are relatively very low when compared to yields obtained in developed Countries e.g. U.S.A. The low yields could be attributed to lack of seeds of improved varieties adapted to the growing zones, low level of technology in the cultural practices and low plant population. In 2008, total cotton production in Nigeria was put at 98,000 metric tones (Spore, 2009).

The quality of cotton lint is very important to the spinning and weaving industry because it determines the use to which it is put. Good quality cotton consist of long, fine, strong lint hairs, free from trash and aborted ovules or immature seeds. They are used to make cotton wool, paper and many other industrial products, (Cobley, 1956). Cotton seed contains up to 30% semi-drying oil and 16-20% protein. Cotton seed oil is one of the most important of the world's semi-drying oils, after it has been refined; the oil is used for cooking, in manufacture of hard substitutes and in soap making.

Cotton research especially in the area of genetics is very vital to the increase yielding ability of locally developed cotton varieties, which makes it very attractive and profitable to farmers, thus stimulate their interest in cotton production. The need for more adapted high yielding varieties cannot be overemphasized especially with the expansion of the textile industry in Nigeria. Emphasis therefore needs to be placed on the cotton breeding so as to enhance its utilization significantly. Meredith *et al.* (1997) and Spore (2009) have reported that breeding progress for increased yields has greatly decreased in recent years therefore; there is the need for more breeding work to improve the cotton plant. Sprague and Tatum (1942) defined General Combining Ability (GCA) as the average

performance of a line in a hybrid combination, and it is a measure of additive gene action. Specific combining Ability (SCA) was defined as those instances in which certain hybrid combination perform relatively better or worse than the average

However, genetic improvement can only be achieved when genetic information about any particular genetic materials is readily available, which the plant breeder can utilize and exploit to achieve fast genetic improvement. It is on the need to enhance the yielding ability of Nigerian cotton, to international standards, that this study is being proposed with the following objective.

1. To estimate the general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) in F_1 cotton genotypes grown in Northeastern Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

EXPERIMENTAL SITE

The study was conducted in two locations in Yola, Adamawa State (Lat. $7^{\circ}11'N$ and Long. $11^{\circ}14'E$) and the other at Sibre Village in Ardo-Kola Local Government Area in Taraba State (Lat. $6^{\circ}30'$ and $9^{\circ}36'N$ and Long $9^{\circ}15'50''$ $10' E$). In Adamawa State, site is located at Lat $9^{\circ}18'$ Long, $12^{\circ}15'E$ has an altitude of 200cm above sea level and is within the Northern Guinea Savannah zone. The soil type is clay loam. Site in Taraba State, is located at longitude $8^{\circ}.30' - 9^{\circ}00'N$, latitude $11^{\circ}.00' - 11^{\circ}.30'$ East of Jalingo, the State capital. It has a temperature range of $30^{\circ}C - 36^{\circ}C$ during the rainy season. The soil is loamy to sandy loam.

Crossing nursery and procedure

Crossing nursery plots were marked out for the eight parents. Seeds of the parental varieties were grown in a $3m \times 3m$ plots at a spacing of $75cm \times 54cm$ to give a total of twenty (20) plants per plot and one hundred and sixty (160) parental plant populations for the eight different parents in a total areas of $961m^2$. Seedlings were thinned to one plant per stand after two weeks of planting. Two split doses of nitrogen fertilizer (N.P.K), was applied at 2 WAS and the second dose at 8WAS. Crosses were carried out among the eight parental varieties in a full diallel mating design to obtain $56F_1$ (direct and reciprocal) crosses. Parental varieties would be obtained through self-pollination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE

The mean squares from the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for combining ability in 8×8 full dialled cross of cotton combined across locations are presented in Table 1. Highly significant location mean squares were

obtained for seed yield and days to maturity. Only days to first flowering had significant (0.05) mean squares for location. No significant mean squares existed in the location for days to 50% flowering, days to boll opening, plant height, boll size, number of bolls per plant, lint percentage and lint yield. Highly significant mean squares existed among crosses and parents for most of the characters except for plant height, boll size and lint percentage. Highly significant reciprocal mean squares were obtained for all the traits except non significant mean squares that were obtained for lint percentage.

Highly significant mean squares existed among parents x crosses for days to first flowering, days to boll opening, number of bolls seed and lint yield. Significant mean squares existed among parents x crosses for days to first flowering, days to boll opening, number of bolls seed and lint yield. Significant mean squares existed for days to 50% flowering. There were no significant mean squares for the other characters. Similarly, highly significant mean squares existed among crosses x reciprocals for most of the characters except for days to 50% flowering, plant height and lint percentage. Significant mean squares existed among parents x reciprocals for all the characters except for plant height and lint percentage. The interaction between parent x reciprocals x crosses showed highly significant mean squares for only four characters namely; days to 50% flowering, seed yield, lint yield and days to maturity. There was no significant interaction for the other characters.

There was highly significant reciprocal x location mean squares for days to boll opening, plant height, boll size, number of bolls per plant, seed yield and days to maturity. No significant mean squares were observed for day to first flowering, days to 50% flowering, lint percentage and lint yield.

Variances for GCA and SCA both appeared important in determining the genetic control of most of the traits investigated. Both GCA and SCA variance mean squares are highly significant for all the traits investigated except for lint percentage. The GCA x location mean squares was highly significant for number of bolls per plant, seed yield and days to maturity.

No significant GCA x location interaction mean squares was observed for days to first flowering, days to 50% flowering, days to boll opening, plant height, boll size, lint percentage and lint yield. SCA x location interaction mean square showed highly significant interaction for days to boll opening, boll size, number of bolls per plant, seed yield and days to maturity. No significant SCA x location interaction was observed for days to first flowering, days to 50% flowering, plant height, lint percentage and lint yield.

GENERAL COMBINING ABILITY OF PARENTS

Characteristics such as yield, earliness are inherited as quantitative traits. The knowledge of genetic structure and mode of inheritance of such complex traits help breeders to employ suitable breeding methodology for

improvement of traits. Dialled analysis has been developed for this purpose and can be used to help answer questions concerning the importance of specific combining ability and the predictability of hybrid performance using general combining ability or parental performance (Rauf *et al.* 2005).

The results, (Table 2), revealed that SAMCOT 9 and SAMCOT 10 proved to be potential by manifesting significant positive GCA effects for days to first flowering. Crossing these two parents therefore will likely produce early flowering hybrids. Similarly, TAMCOTCAMD-E and SAMCOT 13 are good general combiners for days to 50% flowering. If these parents are crossed with SAMCOT 9 and SAMCOT 10 they can produce hybrids that would flower early thereby reducing maturity period. Kimbeng and Nwasike, (1994) and Kukadia *et al.* (1983) reported similar results in pearl millet.

SAMCOT 13, Ex-Benin, SAMCOT 12, TAMCOTCAMD-E and SAMCOT 8 all had a positive GCA effects for number of bolls per plant, which means crossing these parents will likely result in hybrids with more number of bolls per plant therefore more yield. Islam *et al.* (2007) reported that high yielding parents having high GCA effects produce better hybrids combinations. For plant height, SAMCOT 13 was the only best general combiner as well as one of the best general combiner for days to boll opening, boll size and number of bolls per plant. It was concluded that better general combiners for most of the traits should be exploited in the varietal improvement programme, SAMCOT 13 is hereby recommended for exploiting in breeding programme for improvement since it showed potential for most of the traits. (Marani, 1967; Konoplya and Fursor, 1976; Singh *et al.* 1989; Hussain and Kahn, 1991; Kahn *et al.*, 1991a). All the other parental lines had a negative GCA effect for plant height. Negative GCA effect for plant height could also be desirable. Shorter plant height has a lot of advantage in windy and stormy regions in order to withstand lodging. Positive GCA effect exhibited by SAMCOT 13 for plant height on the other would also be desirable. And so, crossing SAMCOT 13 with the other parents would likely lead to the production of taller plants with more branches and more bolls. SAMCOT 9 was the best combiner for boll size and TAMCOTCAMD-E and SAMCOT 13. These parents when crossed can produce good hybrids with larger boll size and eventually higher yield. The parental lines SAMCOT 10, SAMCOT 8, SAMCOT 11 and SAMCOT 12 were the best general combiners for seed yield and SAMCOT 8 was the best general combiner for lint yield. So, crossing SAMCOT 8 with either of these parents will result in an increase in seed yield as well as lint yield in their hybrids. High GCA effect for days to maturity was recorded by SAMCOT 8, SAMCOT 9 and SAMCOT 11 which also suggests that hybrids from these parents would result in shorter or longer days to maturity. The high variance due to GCA for all the traits measured in this study suggests an additive gene action for yield components. Similar results were reported by Saifullah *et al.* (2009), Zia -UL-Islam, (2001), Abo-EL-

Zahab and Metwaly (1979), Bhatade *et al.* (1980), Duhoon and Singh, (1983), Singh *et al.* (1989). This study found that the parent SAMCOT 13 is the best general combiner followed by SAMCOT 8, SAMCOT 9 and TAMCOTCAMD-E for most of the yield and yield components, therefore they should produce desirable segregates for selection when crossed together. Alabi *et al.* (1987) suggested that parents found to be good general combiners for different characters should be extensively used in hybridization programme. Echekwu and Alabi, (1994) also suggested that parents with positive GCA effects should contribute positive additive effects to their progeny. Other lines which show average to high GCA for yield and are components may possess favorable genes for these traits and could be exploited in breeding programmes. In cotton and in most of the other important crops such as cowpea, sorghum etc, Moll and Stuber (1974) concluded that genetic variability in the most important traits in autogamous crops are predominantly additive.

SPECIFIC COMBINING ABILITY EFFECTS OF HYBRIDS

The specific combining ability effects are usually used to identify the best cross combinations for hybrid production. This study revealed that hybrids with high SCA effects involved at least one or both high general combiners as parents. In other words, most crosses with high SCA effects involved at least one of the high general combiners viz; SAMCOT 8, SAMCOT 9, SAMCOT 10, SAMCOT 11, SAMCOT 12, SAMCOT 13 and EX-Benin (Table 3). Kadams (1999) reported similar results where a hybrid with high SCA effects involved one or both of the good general combiners as parents SCA effects are brought about the action of non-additive genes. It should be noted that if there are inconsistencies in SCA effects, it is due to environmental effects and therefore it is advisable to try the material in several locations before selection is carried out. The high SCA effect for boll size exhibited by the cross SAMCOT 9 x SAMCOT 11 showed that the parents SAMCOT 9 and SAMCOT 11 had the potential of generating high yielding segregates. The results are in accordance with the findings of earlier researchers (Abo-El-Zahab and Metwaly, 1979; Desai, 1980; Hussain and Khan, 1991 and Khan *et al.* 1991).

The SCA effects of yield components for crosses revealed that the hybrid SAMCOT 9 x SAMCOT 11 proved to be the best for boll size, and the parent SAMCOT 9 also appeared among the best hybrid for number of bolls per plant as well as for days to maturity. It is obvious from these results in three combinations involving SAMCOT 9, as one of the best combiner with the higher parental value for these traits in questions; boll size, number of bolls per plant and days to maturity showing possibility of importance through careful selection. Similar result was reported by Saifullah *et al.* (2009).

The study identified the hybrid SAMCOT 8 x SAMCOT 12 to be the best for days to first flowering, also one of the best for days to 50% flowering and TAMCOTCAMD-E x SAMCOT 12 the best hybrid with the highest lint yield. In all these three combinations, SAMCOT 12 appeared to be one of the parents, therefore exploring the potentials of SAMCOT 12 could lead to an improvement in hybrids for earliness and higher lint yield, with the intention of developing cultivars for earliness in flowering and higher yield Cheatham, *et al.* (2003), this hybrid seem to be desirable for this purpose. The low levels of SCA effects imply that dominance gene action was not appreciable. The high and low levels of GCA and SCA effects in this analysis agrees with the results of Elden *et al.* (1986), who also reported high and low GCA and SCA effects in cowpea.

These good materials identified could be bulked together to generate population for the improvement of important yield and yield traits in cotton.

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Cite this Article: Simon SY, Kadams AM, Aliyu B (2013). Combining Ability Analysis in F+ Hybrids of Cotton (*Gossypium Species* L.) by Diallel Method in Northeastern Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences,* 3(2): 090-096, <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJAS.GJAS.2013.2.101812119>.

TABLE 1: Mean squares of the analysis of variance for combining ability in a 8x8 diallel cross of F₁ hybrids, combined across locations

Source of variation		Days to First	Days to 50%	Days to boll	Plant height	Boll size	No of boll	Lint %	Seed %	Lint yield	Days to yield
maturity	Df	Flowering	Flowering	opening	(m)	(cm)			(g)	(g)	
LOCATION	1	4.00*	2.36	0.79	0.09	0.61	2.27	0.46	15.24**	1.78	21.47**
REP/LOCATION	4	1.80	4.11*	3.61*	30.86**	21.75**	10.95**	0.07	33.78**	3.95*	8.17**
CROSSES	27	31.33**	44.75**	201.95**	0.38	1.52	61.39**	0.44	246.44**	5.73**	
180.34**											
PARENTS	7	18.09**	17.89**	186.69**	0.35	1.42	38.27**	0.75	182.02**	23.39**	229.89
RECIPROCAL	27	42.05**	55.11**	431.71**	295.10**	83.20**	173.37**	1.08	278.05**	16.20**	420.28**
ENTRIES	35	27.81**	39.62**	340.14**	24.82**	66.66**	74.17**	1.02	206.02**	18.22**	276.98**
LOCATION X ENTRIES	35	0.81	1.19	4.82**	0.03	6.23**	15.59**	0.07	15.19**	0.65	15.36**
CROSSES X LOCATION	35	2.26	1.74	9.19**	244.47**	24.73**	15.18**	0.06	20.19**	6.50*	37.09**
PARENTS X LOCATION	1	0.00	0.09	61.57**	0.10	14.39**	4.25*	0.19	12.94**	0.00	26.91**
PARENTS X CROSSES	1	7.64**	2.79*	51.33**	0/02	1.27	69.36**	0.00	153.27**	8.84**	0.82
RECIPROCAL X LOCATION	28	0.76	0.97	9.26**	5.04**	5.63**	16.46**	0.13	20.41**	0.64	21.22**
PARENTS X CROSSES X LOCATION	1	0.12	4.83**	1.12	0.00	0.75	0.65	0.00	67.79**	21.03**	169.50**
GCA	7	26.6**	13.92*	325.95**	192.87**	29.29**	154.9**	2.00	208.86**	25.77**	455.36**
SCA	28	28.07**	45.06*	161.07**	250.65**	64.76**	48.78**	0.73	148.30**	13.57**	86.80**
GCA X LOCATION	7	0.83	0.82	0.73	0.01	1.13	9.03**	0.14	9.98**	1.37	18.36**
SCA X LOCATION	28	0.74	1.33	5.47**	0.03	6.13	15.09**	0.05	15.60**	0.48	15.54**
POOLED ERROR	70										

TABLE 2: Estimates of general combining ability effects for yield traits in parents, combined across locations

S/n	Parental lines	Days to First Flowering	Days to 50% Flowering	Days to boll opening	Plant height (m)	Boll size (cm)	No of boll plant	Lint %	Seed yield (g)	Lint yield (g)	Days to maturity
1.	SAMCOT 8	-1.601	-0.788	1.541	-0.925	-1.097	-3.089	-0.334	2.910	1.715	7.887
2.	SAMCOT 9	1.373	0.407	-5.864	-1.428	2.636	-3.726	-0.163	-4.804	-1.385	3.305
3.	SAMCOT 10	1.343	1.289	10.815	-2.030	-0.164	-4.362	0.168	5.151	0.600	-1.469
4.	TAMCOTCAMD-E	0.946	1.880	2.257	-2.685	1.086	-2.491	1.045	-6.819	0.205	-0.773
5.	SAMCOT 13	-0.444	-0.547	8.119	14.950	0.627	6.680	-0.008	-0.028	-0.122	-2.379
6.	EX-BENIN	-1.192	-1.494	4.844	-1.007	-0.111	3.073	-0.413	-0.759	-0.511	-7.444
7.	SAMCOT 11	-0.723	-1.216	-2.128	-5.676	-2.766	3.776	-0.394	2.364	-0.886	1.594
8.	SAMCOT 12	0.298	0.469	2.045	-1.196	-0.21	0.140	0.100	1.986	0.383	-0.720
	SE	0.03	0.02	1.25	0.42	0.11	1.62	0.021	1.02	0.32	1.54

TABLE 3: Estimates of specific combining ability effects for yield and yield traits in F₁ hybrids, combined across locations.

S/n	Hybrids	Pedigree	Days to First Flowering	Days to 50% flowering	Days to boll opening	Plant height (m)	Boll size (cm)	No of bolls plant	Lint %	Seed yield (g)	Lint yield (g)	Days to maturity	
1.	1 x 2	SAMCOT 8 X SAMCOT 9	-1.542	-1.517		0.036	0.563	-0.865	2.214	-0.068	0.617	0.710	-0.301
2.	1 x 3	SAMCOT 8 X SAMCOT 10	-1.147	0.049		0.544	0.722	0.250	2.068	0.052	-0.318	-0.307	0.357
3.	1 x 4	SAMCOT 8 X TAMCOTCAMD-E	-0.574	0.567		0.312	0.664	0.182	1.575	0.063	5.257	-0.967	-2.476
4.	1 x 5	SAMCOT 8 X SAMCOT 13	0.294	-0.149		-0.453	-2.524	0.284	-2.220	-0.159	-3.558	-0.203	-0.300
5.	1 x 6	SAMCOT 8 X EX-BENIN	0.211	-0.258		0.640	0.563	0.275	-4.177	0.166	0.143	-0.539	1.045
6.	1 x 7	SAMCOT 8 X SAMCOT 11	1.236	0.874		-1.541	-1.355	-0.624	0.107	0.085	-2.326	-0.071	-2.433
7.	1 x 8	SAMCOT 8 X SAMCOT 12	2.348	1.943		-1.608	0.700	0.151	-0.404	0.073	-2.218	-1.760	1.185
8.	2 x 3	SAMCOT 9 X SAMCOT 10	-0.738	-1.331		4.612	0.558	-1.104	0.405	-0.261	-4.145	-0.291	2.132
9.	2 x 4	SAMCOT 9 X TAMCOTCAMD-E	0.626	-0.396		-2.003	0.713	-0.443	1.703	-0.454	-2.647	0.115	-0.426
10	2 x 5	SAMCOT 9 X SAMCOT 13	-1.879	-2.530		-2.726	-2.583	-1.075	-2.842	0.105	-1.052	-0.025	-1.900
11.	2 x 6	SAMCOT 9 X EX-BENIN	1.203	1.026		2.408	0.745	-1.117	-0.341	0.253	3.192	0.047	2.862
12.	2 x 7	SAMCOT 9 X SAMCOT 11	1.061	1.867		2.393	-1.419	7.757	-1.139	0.196	0.055	0.057	0.341
13.	2 x 8	SAMCOT 9 X SAMCOT 12	-0.137	-0.429		-1.442	0.450	-0.792	-0.924	0.011	-0.520	-0.603	-0.847
14	3 x 4	SAMCOT 10 X TAMCOTCAMD-E	-1.937	-3.163		-5.112	0.572	-0.307	-1.524	-0.241	-2.005	-0.139	-0.351
15.	3 x 5	SAMCOT 10 X SAMCOT 13	0.806	1.411		-1.711	-2.312	0.435	-0.154	0.059	0.844	-0.334	-1.741
16.	3 x 6	SAMCOT 10 X EX-BENIN	-0.276	-0.031		-3.200	0.779	0.431	1.221	-0.063	0.922	-0.199	-2.020
17.	3 x 7	SAMCOT 10 X SAMCOT 11	0.040	0.476		-0.799	-1.043	-0.614	0.173	0.084	-0.714	-0.280	-3.666
18.	3 x 8	SAMCOT 10 X SAMCOT 12	0.470	0.311		-2.552	0.275	0.784	-1.324	0.027	2.458	2.432	-2.500
19.	4 x 5	TAMCOTCAMD-E X SAMCOT 13	0.879	0.971		-1.826	-2.428	-0.365	1.060	0.012	4.212	0.138	1.574
20.	4 x 6	TAMCOTCAMD-E X EX-BENIN	0.296	0.320		1.559	0.696	0.113	0.020	0.209	-2.542	0.244	-0.246
21.	4 x 7	TAMCOTCAMD-E X SAMCOT 11	-0.970	-0.963		4.752	-1.172	-0.669	0.013	-0.200	3.320	0.175	0.524
22.	4 x 8	TAMCOTCAMD-E X SAMCOT 12	0.918	2.351		6.044	-0.004	1.711	-1.833	0.420	0.709	0.140	0.475
23.	5 x 6	SAMCOT 13 X EX-BENIN	0.248	0.394		-0.622	-2.425	0.331	1.057	-0.063	-0.359	0.108	1.279
24.	5 x 7	SAMCOT 13 X SAMCOT 11	-0.059	0.110		1.820	1.498	-0.631	-0.449	0.084	-0.496	0.089	-0.532
25.	5 x 8	SAMCOT 13 X SAMCOT 12	-0.456	-1.171		6.111	2.727	0.630	1.826	-0.148	0.013	0.407	1.145
26.	6 x 7	EX-BENIN X SAMCOT 11	-0.476	-0.540		0.002	-1.319	-0.602	0.385	0.039	-2.001	0.203	0.272
27.	6 x 8	EX-BENIN X SAMCOT 12	-0.788	-0.738		-1.434	0.389	0.260	1.108	-0.189	-0.238	-0.0162	-2.361
28.	7 x 8	SAMCOT 11 X SAMCOT 12	-0.546	-0.667		-5.183	-5.365	-3.029	0.863	-0.130	0.217	-0.425	2.117
		SE	0.67	0.66		2.11	0.87	3.54	1.01	0.25	1.53	1.43	0.82